

1 **Discovery science in cervical cancer with transcriptomics.**

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6 We used transcriptomics for discovery of gene products that define the cervical cancer gene signature.
7 We describe here key differences in the cell polarity and junctional biology program including activation of
8 *Ajuba* and *Tjp1* in cervical cancer. Cervical cancer cell lines were defined by their expression of the
9 immune and cell surface receptors *Tyro3* and *Pvr*.

10 Citations

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